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Learning Loss Problems of Students Based on the Teachers and Parents' Perspectives as the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* Actors During Online Learning

Bagas Narendra Parahita¹, Ghufonudin², Dwi Astutik³, Yuhastina⁴, Riadi Syaputra Siregar⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Department of Sociology Antropology Education, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Central Java, Indonesia

Correspondence: Department of Sociology Antropology Education, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Central Java, Indonesia. E-mail: bagasnarendrap@staff.uns.ac.id

Abstract

Tri Sentra Pendidikan has faced challenges during the pandemic. Teachers and parents as actors in the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* or Three Centers of Education were close to the problem of learning loss during the pandemic. The limitations of learning dared to cause teachers and students to experience obstacles in the process of conveying and receiving learning knowledge. Parents could not be fully present in the learning process at home with the complexity of home activities that have changed since the pandemic situation. Qualitative research with a phenomenological approach was conducted on eight informants consisting of four teachers and four parents from various regions in Indonesia. The research results indicated that teachers and parents, and character education, were significant to note because of the link between learning loss and the development of children's character. Teachers and parents must ensure the effective use of technology for learning used by children in addition to the technological mastering skills by current students. It was because children's technological skills could be a solution to minimize learning loss if the practice or used as directed by teachers and parents who were actively paying attention and controlling. Teachers and parents, as actors in the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan*, must know the students' characteristics to determine the right strategy for the development of student education.

Keywords: Learning, Students, *Tri Sentra Pendidikan*, Online Learning

1. Introduction

The development of the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant effect on the health, economy, and education sectors globally. Based on data from the *Central Bureau of Statistics* (BPS) in 2020, the pandemic has affected the economic condition of the people in Indonesia by 2.07 percent (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2020) Furthermore, other data from the Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) showed that the open unemployment rate in Indonesia in 2021 in February was recorded to have increased by 06.26 percent. (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2021) The decline in various economic indicators could impact the condition of education in Indonesia during the pandemic.

Problems faced by educational actors ranged from families, teachers, students, and the community. The high unemployment rate and the increasing economic downturn affected the parents' ability to provide learning facilities for their children, especially on the *online* learning system that relied heavily on technology and the internet. If these two components cannot be met, the children's learning process will be disrupted, so their learning achievement is not optimal. It will result in groups in the vulnerable category who have been left behind in the quality of their education due to difficult economic conditions so that children's education will be set aside to pay for their daily lives (Santosa, 2020) Additionally, such conditions can result in students not understanding the material being taught because they cannot follow the learning process optimally.

The challenge faced by students was being in intense competition in the era of demographic bonuses. Another problem faced by teachers and students was that they must adapt to various communication and information technology innovations to achieve educational goals (Yuhastina et al., 2020) It was also inseparable from the parents' busyness at work, so they did not have enough time to monitor their children's learning progress (Sukarman, 2020) In this case, education actors as social system units need to collaborate to minimize various problems that occur during online learning.

Long before the educational situation worsened during the current pandemic, historically, education in Indonesia, in general, has had a *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* or Three Centers of Education approach conveyed by Ki Hajar Dewantara, which was an educational concept which sees that children have a learning environment that can be the center of education and is vital for their development, namely the family environment, school environment, and community environment (Dewantara, 2013) However, the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* concept encountered challenges during the pandemic. One of the challenges was the implementation of *Community Activity Restrictions* (PPKM) and significant changes in the learning process, which were carried out in offline schools but had to be done online at home.

Various impacts are feared to lead to a situation that could result in a *lost generation* because children cannot study in school and carry out social activities as before. *Lost generation* occurs due to *learning loss* or *loss of learning quality* in implementing the online learning system. It happens because the teachers find it difficult to directly monitor the development of their students in the implementation process, both in cognitive, psychomotor, or character development. Much research revealed that the implementation of online learning was only to abort obligations. One of them was evidenced by the fact that teachers often give excessive assignments without explaining the material concept (Kuncoro, 2020) In addition, there were even students who were not present when distance learning took place because the network did not support it, or it could also be caused by students who felt bored with an ineffective learning system (Hakim & Azis, 2021). Other research has also revealed that all students might not understand the core material delivered online. Students will understand based on their point of view because their understanding is less comprehensive (Asmuni, 2020) It means that it can be said that the lost generation caused by online learning that does not work well will result in learning loss and have a bad effect on student learning development.

Loss of knowledge and skills experience academic setbacks due to differences or prolonged gaps in the educational process. Even though various technologies support online learning, gaps still lead to less effective learning at home (Andriani et al., 2021) As time went by, online learning was considered less effective for most students, which has resulted in *Learning Loss*. Mentoring is needed intensely in various learning ecosystems, in this case, between educational actors.

It means that synergy and cooperation from various parties, especially the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan*, are needed through a good strategy so that the condition of Indonesia's education can quickly improve. Hence, the orientation of superior human resources and advanced Indonesia in 2045 can be achieved. Therefore, based on the various problems that have been presented, this research had a novelty and objective in providing an overview of the student learning loss problems based on the teachers' and parents' perspectives when learning online in Indonesia.

1.1 Theoretical Framework

The psychoanalytic theory approach proposed by Sigmund Freud was considered appropriate to explore the research focus. The psychoanalytic theory developed by Sigmund Freud is a theory that seeks to explain the nature and development of the human personality. This theory emphasizes internal elements such as motivation and emotions that can affect the development of the human personality, namely when conflicts occur from these psychological aspects, which generally occur in children or at an early age (Helaludin & Syahrul, 2019). Like the *learning loss* experienced by students, the problems they experience while carrying out online learning lead to aspects of decreasing learning motivation and increasing emotions in these students.

A decrease in motivation can occur due to a lack of interaction, attention, and direct guidance from both teachers and parents of students. Furthermore, the implementation of psychoanalytic theory in the world of education is divided into six matters relating to the *learning loss* experienced by students due to online learning, including the concept of anxiety, the educational process based on multiple intelligences, the psychoanalytic concept, which states that humans are creatures with basic needs and desires, students' aggressiveness, gaps due to differences of each student's background, as well as the students' creativity. Education in the concept of psychoanalysis refers to all actions taken by adults, experts or non-experts, teachers, and parents to form the students' behavior in their growth period through desired ways (Sukaesih et al., 2022) Through education, a person will compete and motivate him to be the best in all his life aspects.

The educational objectives based on psychoanalytic analysis, among others, provide direction to educators and students about what they want to achieve, actions or activities carried out, and the progress students achieved (Helaludin & Syahrul, 2019). The relationship between psychoanalysis and education is very complex, meaning that psychoanalysis has undergone many developments and enriched the level of behavior in the educational relationship (Conia & Sofiyanti, 2021). It is highly correlated with the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan*, which emphasizes that the education centers for children consist of the family, school, and community environment.

2. Method

The research method was qualitative with a phenomenological approach. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with parents of students from various economic and professional backgrounds, the school through teachers, as members of the community unit to see the complexity of the *learning loss* problem.

The interview questions given focused on the complexity of the experiences of *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* actors in minimizing the occurrence of *learning loss* in students. Primary data obtained by the researcher using a semi-structured interview procedure provided an opportunity for the informants to describe the experiences in depth by always guiding the interview procedure and process (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

The primary informants consisted of four teachers and four parents. The complexity of the different backgrounds of each informant was under the research objective, namely to get perspectives on the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* actors' experiences in minimizing learning loss. All interviews were recorded based on the informants' consent. Furthermore, the researcher checked the recordings repeatedly to ensure the authenticity of the information or data provided by the informants when transcribing the results of the interviews.

The data analysis technique was narrative analysis which focused on the text that explained the story of the informants about a phenomenon being studied by going through three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. These stages were done to see the various problems and challenges to overcome *learning loss* based on the teachers' and parents' perspectives so that verified conclusions could be drawn.

The interview excerpts presented in this article represented the various data obtained. Not all of the results were comprehensive. Only interview excerpts were considered critical data. The other data were described in the narrative of the research results and discussion analysis.

3. Results

The results showed that various limitations of online learning caused both teachers and students to experience obstacles in the process of conveying and receiving learning knowledge. The limitations were the quality of the transfer of knowledge process that could not be maximized, causing learning loss in students. The difficulties experienced by some students were believed to be due to boredom, fatigue, internet connection problems, facilities, and various other things that hindered online learning. It made students less active and not enthusiastic about participating in learning practices at home.

Online learning that could not be maximized then presented its challenges for teachers in creating effective learning to achieve learning goals. Online learning with various forms of limitations caused various problems faced by both teachers and students, even parents and schools. The informant said that the obstacles faced caused learning achievement to be not optimal due to obstacles in long-distance communication resulting in teachers not being able to control student activities. Hence, it had implications for students to be lazy to participate in online learning.

Distance learning that could not be maximized caused material delivery not to reach the target. One of the informants, who was also a teacher at a public school in Surakarta City, said that the school, together with homeroom teachers and teachers, has collaborated to deal with this problem by communicating through students' parents and following up by conducting home visits if needed. The informants mentioned that distance learning was convenient for delivering more explicit material. Simplification of learning could be in tasks that did not burden students. There were various perspectives from teachers and parents related to the learning loss problems experienced by high school and junior high school students.

3.1 *The Challenge of Strengthening Character Education was Important to Overcome Learning Loss*

School closures are carried out in response to the pandemic situation, and the learning process must be carried out online with all the problems in the family environment. It gave the potential for teachers to have difficulty seeing children's development. The vulnerable situation was that the children did not get the maximum attention from the teachers regarding the learning development. It impacts the occurrence of *Learning Loss* initiated by the sparse character education given to children. It was conveyed by one of the teacher informants who taught at a senior high school in Jepara Regency (Interviewee 1):

"Learning Loss could happen to anything, especially in character. Due to distance learning, (teachers) could not do character education directly for students. Many obstacles arose during the implementation of study from home or distance learning. Schools sometimes did not know for sure what the actual physical and social conditions of the students were because we (the teacher) met only through tools through technology. We (teachers) did not understand the real situation or condition of the students." - Interviewee 1.

It should be noted that the potential for *learning loss* did not only occur when children learned independently when *studying from home*, but face-to-face learning has occurred before the pandemic. Limited face-to-face learning with an inappropriate learning strategy approach also caused it. However, the pandemic has exacerbated the *learning loss* experienced in the educational environment. It meant the cooperation of various parties was vital to prepare students to be released from *learning loss* situations.

Schools must immediately identify the circumstances and conditions of learning loss in various learning situations individually and in groups (*face-to-face learning, distance learning, blended learning, etc.*). It must be done considering that students will face an open and dynamic educational competition situation. The following is a statement from a teacher informant who taught in senior high school in Musi Banyuasin Regency (Interviewee 2) and from a senior high school teacher informant in Karanganyar Regency (Interviewee 3):

"Learning loss occurred in almost all aspects, both cognitive, skill, character, and social. Sure, it was not in all students, but most of the students, for example, for the cognitive and skill aspects, which I said above. About the characters, the students' temperament was not well controlled. About social concerns, there was very little concern, etc." - Interviewee 2.

"The problem was related to distance learning. Teachers could not control students' activities in learning optimally because distance communication was deep. Not all students were maximal in understanding the material and assignments given by the teacher," -Interviewee 3.

It can be seen that the problem of learning loss was very complex from the experience felt by the informants as teachers. Cognitive problems, skills, character, and even social relationships become a single problem students face when learning online during a pandemic. Communication barriers became one of the obstacles when students tried to follow task instructions or understand the knowledge provided by the teacher.

3.2 Parents' difficulties and solutions in monitoring their children's learning process when learning online

Parents had difficulty giving the leading role as educators in the home environment. Assistance from parents tended to be unaware that students needed their attention, motivation, and support. Concerning cognitive, if the learning ecosystem situation in the home environment has been created well, students could develop positive independent learning. The following are some of the problems and solutions presented by one of the informants from the students' parents from Pekalongan Regency:

"Sometimes, I found it difficult because the understanding of parents and children was different. Therefore, parents should browse google when having trouble understanding children's learning material. It was different when at school. Some teachers explained and understood the material clearly. In addition, parents were also busy with homework and office work so that it was certainly not optimal to master their children's learning materials" -Interviewee 6.

Parents said that the understanding between them and their children was different. In this case, it could represent a tendency for the distance between generations. In addition to the busyness of parents at home due to various work obligations, parents must understand children's learning materials if needed because the presence, participation, and role of parents as children's learning partners when learning was needed to support children's confidence. A student's parent conveyed another thing as the informant who came from Surakarta City:

"Everyone must know about children. They could not focus on learning. They must play a lot. It was also impossible that children only learned, they must play a lot." -Interviewee 8.

One of the parent informants from Surakarta City said that when online learning was carried out, children were easily distracted from their learning focus. It was due to the children's inability to set priorities and the parents' inability to monitor children during learning. Disturbances could occur from various things, such as dependence on access to various information or entertainment contained in smartphones. The following problems were conveyed by one of the students' parents from Sukoharjo Regency:

"If it was online, there was an opportunity to ask a friend. There was difficulty communicating with each other. In school, there was a teacher. So, children must be happy with online learning" -Interviewee 7.

Children will contact colleagues if they find it challenging to learn the material. It proved that there was a tendency that children as independent students when learning online at home still be very dependent on peers when studying online. Home conditions with their respective problems could also be a different obstacle for students. They could cause *Learning Loss*, where students cannot focus on the explanation of the material from the teacher.

The research results also showed a *Learning Loss* process due to problems with internet connections which significantly interfered with students' focus on understanding the learning material, both delivered by the teacher

and other friends during presentations when studying from home. In addition, students could also feel *Learning Loss* due to the lack of interaction and socialization with friends and the intensity of communication with the teacher, which was felt to be very minimal in duration.

4. Discussion

Teachers and parents, as actors in the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan*, must know the characteristics to determine the right strategy for the educational development of students. In this case, the priority of educational attainment must have strengthened in terms of character or attitude in various conditions. The success of a child's learning process does not depend on educational institutions. However, there is also the effect of the family, which is one of the educational centers that play an essential role in determining children's achievements (Nurbaiti et al., 2021) However, it should be noted that online learning has advantages that other learning models do not have.

Online learning has the flexibility of space and time. Students can follow the learning that is done anywhere and anytime. Students can explore the needs of knowledge, skills, competencies freely. With flexible learning, students can manage their own study time. A conducive learning atmosphere that uses varied learning methods and styles effectively overcomes student boredom (Elihami & Ibrahim, 2019) Not all learning can be transferred in an online learning environment (Pilkington, 2018). However, if learning loss is not immediately addressed, it will affect the level of student anxiety. It is related to psychoanalytic theory, where the educational process must be based on an awareness of the importance of education that students must undergo amid a pandemic situation.

In connection with the finding that students tend to take advantage of their free time when studying and are at risk of becoming one of the inhibiting factors for learning quality, it seems that it is part of the rationalization process and a reaction to student boredom in the online learning process that is followed daily. Before the pandemic, students were greatly helped by the social conditions of peer-to-peer learning classes, but during the pandemic, students were required to be independent. One of the teacher's strategies to motivate students to study at home is to publish student work (Fadlilah, 2020). A good rationalization process found in this research was when students had the awareness to take advantage of the communication platform for ensuring their understanding of the knowledge being studied with their peers and subject teachers.

Students can avoid learning loss in a *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* environment that supports each other as the foundation for multiple intelligences. With a psychoanalytic approach, students still have to get input and direction from various points of view in self-development, especially in the online learning process, namely with teachers and parents.

In this case, parents play a role in guiding students' attitudes and skills, as well as academically. Parental assistance is significant in online learning because it affects children's awareness of maintaining good learning habits. In this context, the role of parents is always vital to accompany the online learning process (Rahmania et al., 2021). Not optimal mentoring makes children unconsciously free to do bad things to themselves during the learning process, such as lazing around. The form of the parent's role is a form of the teacher's role at school, such as providing motivation in everything, being a happy friend for learning, helping in solving problems and difficulties faced by children while studying, and developing children's self-confidence (Gusmaniarti & Suweleh, 2019; Lilawati, 2020) Parents need to form a disciplined attitude in children because, during online learning, children's play and study time tend to be messy. Familiarizing children by setting a good example is a role that parents can play when the education situation is centered from home (Lase et al., 2021) Character education is the creation of a school environment that helps students in developing ethics, responsibility through models, and teaching good character through universal values (Berkowitz, 2021). Therefore, parents have a role to be role models for children, outside the role of teachers during the learning process (Erzad, 2018). Ki Hajar Dewantara said that all places could be used as places of learning, meaning that the potential of a home or family can be the development of student independence.

It is necessary to strengthen the collaboration of *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* that can help students learn in various situations. The formation of personality must still be considered by parents when children study at home so that students are aware of the primary purpose of a quality learning process. It is vital for forming the children's

personalities (Wahidin, 2019) The sustainability of future learning must be close to the needs of generations. The proximity of students to technology opens up opportunities that online learning is one of the options for developing learning that must be responded to sustainably. An adaptive curriculum can facilitate students' skills in the 21st century. A curriculum can be implemented in schools, homes, and the wider community. The educational approach must refer to technology, namely from the digitalization of education. In this case, education through the digitalization of education provides an opportunity for the community as one of the actors in the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* to play an essential role in minimizing learning loss.

5. Conclusion

Learning loss was not a new problem, and it could happen to all people from various backgrounds in social, economic, geographical situations, etc. *Learning loss* during a pandemic could worsen if students could not make the best use of their time even though facilities and infrastructure were available. *Learning loss* could also worsen when students lack attention, external support, and self-motivation. Thus, it could be understood that learning loss was a complex problem and could be analyzed from various points of view. One of them was the characteristic of the millennial generation who have experienced an online learning event. Simplification and adjustment of the learning process must always be adapted to the needs of generations.

It was done to ensure that the community was ready to face the next crisis in education. Right on target policies were essential, and school problems must be addressed immediately. The main recommendation is that digital platforms and utilizing an effective digital environment must also be used in teaching in classrooms or schools. Second, education providers and schools must continue to update digital tools and infrastructure. In addition, the *Tri Sentra Pendidikan* environment requires a socio-emotional skill approach through fortitude, curiosity, resilience, emotional regulation, and social competence of students, teachers, and principals to support active participation and welfare of educational actors. Teachers, parents, and the community need to develop a learning ecosystem in the tri center of education by adjusting the learning situation, modifying learning practices, target achievement results, to adjusting the curriculum according to the economic, social, and geographical needs of the local culture so that *learning loss* can be minimized.

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